

GOALS AND TASKS OF ORGANIZING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the inclusion of children with special needs in general education institutions to develop new teaching methods that are more child-centered and more inclusive, and to create opportunities for such children.*

Keywords: *child, education, training, qualification, need, problem, institution, healthy, special, inclusive education, parents, disabled, life, correctional.*

Solving the problem of equal rights in the education and upbringing of children with special needs is one of the urgent problems of today. But even today, many children are left out of education for various reasons. It is necessary to consider the organizational, scientific and methodical measures of involvement in inclusive education, that is, to develop activities related to the training of specialists and improvement of their qualifications. There are specific main factors for attracting children with special needs to general education institutions:

Children with special needs have the right to interact with healthy children. Inclusive education should be organized in an appropriate manner, because children with special needs are socially in need of help, and we need to treat disabled children with more kindness and attention. It is clear to me that such children have the right to study and be educated side by side with their healthy children. Because the laws provide them with the necessary material and moral resources and guarantee their implementation. It is required that parents, neighborhood pedagogues and specialists work together to educate children with disabilities. This is a task, duty and obligation for all of us. We need to work together in the implementation of these tasks.

Children with special needs can work together with their healthy peers, learn, learn and develop at the level of their abilities. If inclusive education is organized appropriately, children with special needs are protected from the social side, feel that they have equal rights in social life, and that they can learn together with their peers.

In the special type of institutions established for children with special needs, children's existing defects should be corrected to a much higher level and they should be adapted to the social society. The reason is that in the future, they will not face difficulties in functioning as children with normal development. Special schools should pay great attention to these aspects. In addition, the fact that children with special needs live in isolation from the general public can be a reason for their inability to adapt to the social environment. The more he interacts with his peers in society, the more flexible he becomes. Because children with special needs have the same rights as healthy children.

The need to attract children with special needs to general education institutions is manifested in the fact that children with special needs who are completely excluded from the education system, because their place of residence is too far away to go to special institutions, or financial resources Helping parents who are struggling due to the lack of education or parents' unwillingness to send their children to a special institution, early and complete adaptation of

children with special needs to social society, solving the issue of equal rights, and preventing discrimination.

Inclusive education allows children with special needs to always be in their family neighborhood and in the circle of relatives. Placement of children in boarding schools far from their family and home prevents their right to participate in the life of their home, family and community. A child who is far from his home, family, and parental love grows up with a hard time. Because the family is the main center of education. The inclusion of children with special needs in general education institutions encourages students to develop new teaching methods that are more child-centered and more inclusive.

Goals and tasks to be solved in inclusive education

In the inclusive education system, it is necessary to solve the following goals and tasks: to create the necessary psychological-pedagogical and correctional conditions for the education of children and adolescents with disabilities in the educational institution, through the implementation of general education programs and correctional work aimed at their abilities spiritual development, implementation of social adjustment;

guaranteeing students' right to equality in education;

meeting the needs of disabled and healthy children with the active participation of society and family, early adaptation to social life;

realization of the right of children and adolescents with disabilities to live without separation from their families;

is the formation of a friendly and loving attitude towards children and adolescents with limited opportunities in the society.

The main principles of inclusion in inclusive education and their content

The implementation of the educational system always requires the basis of certain laws and principles. The implementation of the inclusive education system is based on the following principles:

- 1) Recognition of inclusive education.
- 2) The principle of inclusive education being open to all.
- 3) The principle of existence of connection.
- 4) The principle of decentralization.
- 5) The principle of a comprehensive approach to inclusive education.
- 6) The principle of flexibility in inclusive education.
- 7) Qualification principle.

1. The principle of recognition of inclusive education.

The essence of this principle is that since 1990, several declarations and decisions have been made on the world level regarding the education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions. Many countries of the world recognized them. But to date there are many problems in their implementation. In some countries, when laws or decisions on general education are adopted, the issue of education of disabled children is not included in it. But the recognition of inclusive education will not depend only on passing laws. Fighting discrimination and social prejudice is the most important thing. In other words, the first thing to do is to promote inclusive education among the population.

2. The principle of inclusive education being open to all.

Over the past twenty years, significant work has been done on the education of children with special needs in the system of general education institutions. However, the implementation of the inclusive education system is mainly at the urban level, and in rural areas, children with special needs are still excluded from education, or parents in rural areas face difficulties to ensure that their children with disabilities attend special institutions in cities. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that the involvement of children with special needs in inclusive education covers all children with special needs in all regions.

3. The principle of availability of connection.

At the heart of the word "accessibility" is the quality of public buildings, especially the accessibility of schools for children with disabilities. A child should not be excluded from regular school because they cannot enter the school building (because the stairs are not wheelchair accessible) or because the school toilet is not wheelchair accessible. Creating such facilities does not require much money. The new school building should be built from the time it was planned, taking into account the needs of children with disabilities. Facilities that are good for children with disabilities do not cause any problems for children with normal development. Creating physical connections serves to solve the main problems of inclusive education.

4. The principle of decentralization.

The content of this principle is expressed using the following two aspects:

A). Inclusive education services should be an integrated part of the general education system.

B). Tasks in an inclusive education system should be decentralized to place responsibility and control on local education authorities, and opportunities should be adapted to local conditions.

Decentralization is important to achieve optimal integration. This is especially true in rural areas. The tasks of inclusive education allow children with disabilities to be with their parents, to receive education in schools close to them, just like their peers. This is important in the formation of their personal qualities. Denying the normal development of a disabled child can lead to more serious situations than the disability itself.

5. The principle of comprehensive approach in inclusive education.

Disabled children should not only be treated as disabled, but should be treated in all aspects. This requires planning education for children with special needs, taking into account the needs that may arise throughout their life. In addition, in inclusive education, it is necessary to carry out parallel work on the acquisition of knowledge and skills, along with the elimination, correction, and compensation of the existing defects of a disabled child. At the heart of this principle is an early approach to children with special needs. The education of children with special needs should not end before they receive primary and secondary special education. Vocational education and higher education of disabled children also needs to be implemented. Because one of the tasks of the inclusive education system is to comprehensively develop children with special needs and ensure all their rights.

6. The principle of flexibility in inclusive education.

The essence of this principle is that the curriculum, programs and textbooks should be flexible to the capabilities of children with special needs. The child's needs for special education should form the basis of any integration activity. Due to the different levels and types of individual needs, such activities are required to be flexible and variable.

7. Qualification principle.

Highly qualified teachers are required to teach in classes where children with special needs are taught inclusively. In addition, the teacher of the inclusive class must have advanced qualifications in the field of defectology.

Ways to support inclusive education

Involvement in inclusive education is one of the global problems. A key part of inclusive education is creating a learning-friendly environment for children to learn. If attention is paid to the life of children with special needs from the first age, i.e. up to the age of 6, much higher results can be achieved. Development of policies suitable for meeting the educational needs of children with disabilities is the basis of supporting inclusive education. The following issues should be resolved in support of inclusive education:

Develop a positive attitude in society. Due to the lack of knowledge about disabled children among people in the society, children with special needs are left out of education. In addition, if the abilities, rights and needs of a disabled child are not regularly appreciated, children develop a negative attitude towards themselves and their abilities.

Development of an inclusive educational environment. The main part of inclusive education is to create a friendly environment for children to learn and study. Children should be able to get to school safely and without difficulties. In addition, instead of adapting the child to the current general education methodology, it is necessary to change the lesson schedule, conditions, methodology, and educational tools. Such changes are not limited to children with special needs. Maybe it will improve the quality of education for children with normal development.

In short, early attention to the child's life will have an effective effect on the child's further development. The image of adults is very important in the development of self-confidence and self-esteem in a child. But many children with special needs grow up and do not meet adults with special needs like them and cannot even imagine what it would be like to grow up. That is why adults with special needs should constantly participate in the education of children with special needs. Because parents with special needs can explain the importance of educating their children. For this, it is necessary to invite adults with special needs to schools. Then they will talk about their achievements in life. As a result, a great opportunity is created to promote inclusive education.

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